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TA'LIMGA VEB PLATFORMALARNI JORIY ETISHNI TAHLIL QILISH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ta'limga axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etish hamda, ta'limni veb platformalar orqali boyitishning bosqichlari, imkoniyatlari va afzalliklari yoritilib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, veb sayt, platforma, kontent, tizim, CMS, domen, host.

ANALYSIS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF WEB PLATFORMS IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the stages, opportunities and advantages of introducing information technologies to education and enriching education through web platforms.

Key words: *education, website, platform, content, system, CMS, domain, host.*

INTRODUCTION. ICT has made a big turn in the education system, now international cooperation or student activities cannot be perceived without ICT. Both hardware and software for introducing ICT into educational processes are being formed.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. The purpose of introducing ICT is to make the educational process more efficient. However, in most cases, a lot of attention is paid to providing the educational environment with computer technology and to the learning of computer technology by teachers and students. Effective use of the computer is considered a complex issue.

First of all, computer technology should be introduced into educational programs and curricula, teacher training, educational process management, and additional infrastructures.

Experiments on the implementation of computer technology in the educational system show that, rather than providing each pupil or student with a laptop, complete computerization of the educational environment, in the classrooms, corridors, student rooms, etc. The introduction of public computers in public places helps students to learn computer technology faster[1].

In the process of applying the computer to the educational process, 2 different issues arise - is it necessary to study the computer, or is it necessary to acquire

knowledge with the help of the computer? It should be said that the computer itself does not give the student anything. It can distract the student, steal extra time, and in a sense, isolate him from group activities[2]. There will be more paperwork, paperwork, and even more paperwork than ever before. And we don't pay enough attention when it comes to making the learning environment effective with computer technology.

Young people, including students and young teachers, believe that computer learning is the key to science, but this thing distracts them so much that they are a little indifferent to the issue of learning the experience of the older generation. And this makes the young people stupid. As a result, there will be no progress in science, but after a long time, people will learn to use computers effectively in their professional activities. Therefore, before implementing ICT in the educational process, it is very important to train teachers to use it effectively. In practice, most teachers shy away from using ICT because they are less familiar with ICT than their students. It is necessary for teachers to thoroughly master any tool that enhances the learning environment.

Only, the transfer of educational literature from paper form to electronic version dramatically expands the information space of students. Availability of a local or Internet network, educational platforms in HEIs is one of the main conditions in modern education.

RESULTS. The introduction of web platforms into education is carried out through Internet technologies, which are currently developing day by day. In particular, teaching processes in education are conducted entirely through online web platforms. Examples of these are currently web platforms such as Moodle[3], Hemis, and LMS, through which both student and teacher activities are conducted online.

In this, the teacher can post all information related to science, including lectures, practical, laboratory exercises, independent study topics, course work topics, and current, intermediate, and final control works related to science, as well as information related to his scientific activities. can post information. At the same time, it will be

possible to manage the subject on the web platform and manage the students of the subjects of education in the system[4].

Students can use the science materials introduced by the teacher to learn and collect points and other opportunities by completing tasks and uploading them to the system.

DISCUSSION. Content management systems can be used to create these web platforms to achieve similar opportunities and advantages, because it is easy to manage the web platform in these content management systems and it is also easier to create websites through these platforms and teach these processes to students.

Wordpress is a freely distributed open source website content management system; Written in PHP; database server - MySQL; Released under the GNU GPL version 2. Applications range from blogs to very sophisticated news sources. The built-in system of "themes" and "plugins" together with a successful architecture allows to design projects of wide functional complexity[5].

USP: Open-Source Content Management System. Wordpress powers a whopping 43.3% of all websites on the internet!

WordPress started as a blogging platform and served as an early form of a website builder. It currently also happens to be one of the most popular Content Management Systems in the design and developer community.

You can build any kind of website on WordPress, be it e-commerce stores or full-fledged forums for discussions.

Due to its immense flexibility, while building websites without much technical knowledge, WordPress has a huge fan following. It hosts an array of free or paid themes and plugins[6].

However, you would need to be in charge of managing the security and management aspect. WordPress itself does not come with inbuilt security but gives the community an advantage to build upon the plugin system that it provides.

Joomla is a content management system (CMS) written in PHP and JavaScript that uses MySQL DBMS or other industry standard relational DBMS as database storage. This is free software distributed under the GNU GPL license.

Tilda Publishing is a block website builder that requires no programming skills. Allows you to create websites, online stores, landing pages, blogs and email newsletters.

Google Sites is a simplified free wiki-based hosting. Available as part of Google Apps. It allows people who need information quickly to use wiki technology to access it. Site users can collaborate and add data from other Google applications, such as Google Docs, Google Calendar, YouTube, Google Photos, and other sources.

The creator of the site can invite other users to collaborate on the site and control their access to materials. The site can be used in private mode, for example, to organize a personal wiki or to keep records of a personal project with access to information only after authorization[7].

Work on the site is done in a visual editor. Choose from 6 themes and several ready-made templates. You can create your own design using a blank sheet of paper.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, we can say that the introduction of ICT in education will facilitate the work of all employees working in this field and even students, and will allow us to get rid of excessive paperwork.

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